

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

STUDENTS' THINKING STYLE AND PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

Students' personality development refers to enhancing their social and emotional well-being, developing their communication and interpersonal skills, and preparing them for future academic and career responsibilities.

The thinking process of the students influences their personal development, too. In this article critical, creative thinking, reasoning process was analyzed according to literature materials. Creative thinking steps and learning approach were examined, and the positive relationship find out between academic achievement and learning approach of students. The previous researches let us determine relation and affect between academic achievement and student personal development. This study can help the teachers, the researchers and school administrators who are working with students' groups.

Keywords: thinking style, reasoning, critical and creative thinking, learning approach, student development.

Thinking involves manipulating and transforming information in memory. We think to form concepts, reason, think critically, make decisions, think creatively, and solve problems. Students can think about concrete things, such as a vacation at the beach or how to win at a video game, or about more abstract subjects, such as the meaning of freedom or identity. They can think about the past, such as what happened to them last month, or about the future, such as what their life will be like in the year 2020.

Reasoning - Reasoning is logical thinking that uses induction and deduction to reach a conclusion.

Inductive Reasoning - Reasoning from the specific to the general is inductive reasoning. It consists of drawing conclusions (forming concepts) about all members of a category based on observing only some of its members (Goswami, 2011; Heit, 2008). Researchers have found that inductive-reasoning skill is often a good predictor of academic achievement (Kinshuk & McNab, 2006). What are some examples of the use of inductive reasoning in classrooms?

When a student in English class reads only a few Emily Dickinson poems and is asked to draw conclusions from them about the general nature of Dickinson's poems, inductive reasoning is being requested. When a student is asked whether a concept in a math class applies to other contexts, such as business or science, again, inductive reasoning is being called for.

Educational psychology research is inductive when it studies a sample of participants to draw conclusions about the population from which the sample is drawn. It is also inductive in that scientists rarely take a single study as strong enough evidence to reach a conclusion about a topic, instead requiring a number of studies on the same topic to have more confidence in a conclusion. Indeed, an important aspect of inductive reasoning is repeated observation. Through repeated

observation, information about similar experiences accumulates to the point that a repetitive pattern can be detected and a more accurate conclusion drawn about it. To study this aspect of inductive reasoning, researchers have examined whether inductive inferences are justified based on evidence about a single instance of two co-occurring events (Kuhn, Katz, & Dean, 2004). When two events occur together in time and space, we often conclude that one has caused the other, despite the possibility that other factors are involved. For example, a parent might conclude, "Harry is a bad influence on my daughter; Sharon didn't drink before she met him." The boy might be the cause, but the event may have been a coincidence. Of course, if there is repeated evidence (for example, every girl Harry has ever gone out with develops a drinking problem), then the argument becomes more persuasive. Consider also a child who observes a black snake and concludes, "All snakes are black." The child's cousin sends him an e-mail about a pet snake she recently bought, and he concludes that the pet snake must be black. However, he clearly has not observed all of the snakes in the world—actually, only one in this case—so he has seen only a small sample of the world's snake population. Of course, he would be forced to change his mind if he saw a gray snake or a white snake. The conclusions drawn as a result of inductive reasoning are never finally certain, only more or less probable. But induction can provide conclusive *negative* results—for example, seeing a yellow snake proves that the assertion "All snakes are black" is *false*. As just stated, inductive conclusions are never entirely certain—that is, they may be inconclusive. An inductive conclusion may be very likely, but there always is a chance that it is wrong, just as a sample does not perfectly represent its population (Kuhn, 2009). Teachers can help students improve their inductive reasoning by encouraging them to consider that the conclusion they reach depends on the quality and the

quantity of the information available. Students often overstate a conclusion, making it more definitive than the evidence indicates. Let's now consider another aspect of inductive reasoning: it is basic to analogies.

An *analogy* is a correspondence between otherwise dissimilar things. Analogies can with already learned concepts. One type of analogy involves formal reasoning and has four parts, with the relation between the first two parts being the same as, or very similar to, the relation between the last two. For example, solve this analogy: Beethoven is to music as Picasso is to . To answer correctly ("art"), you had to induce the relation between Beethoven and music (the former created the latter) and apply this relationship to Picasso (what did he create?). How good are children and adolescents at inductive reasoning? Adolescents are better at many aspects of inductive reasoning than are children, including analogies and false inclusion when generalizing from a single event, but not as good as young adults (Kuhn, 2009).

Deductive Reasoning - In contrast to inductive reasoning, deductive reasoning is reasoning from the general to the specific. When you solve puzzles or riddles, you are engaging in deductive reasoning. When you learn about a general rule and then understand how it applies in some situations but not others, you are engaging in deductive reasoning (Goswami, 2011; Johnson-Laird, 2008). Deductive reasoning is always certain in the sense that if the initial rules or assumptions are true, then the conclusion will be correct (Ricco, 2011).

When educators and psychologists use theories and intuitions to make predictions, then evaluate these predictions by making further observations, they are using deductive reasoning.

Many aspects of deductive reasoning have been studied, including the occasions when knowledge and reasoning conflict. During adolescence, individuals are increasingly able to reason deductively even when the premises being reasoned about are false (Kuhn, 2009). Consider this deductive inference problem: *All basketball players are motorcycle drivers. All motorcycle drivers are women.* Assuming that these two statements are true, decide if the following statement is true or false: *All basketball players are women.*

Children rarely realize that such conclusions are valid deductions from the premises. From early adolescence through early adulthood, individuals improve in their ability to make accurate conclusions when knowledge and reasoning conflict. That is, they can "reason independently of the truth status of the premises" (Kuhn & Franklin, 2006).

Critical thinking - Currently, there is considerable interest in critical thinking among psychologists and educators, although it is not an entirely new idea (Assaf, 2009; Bensley & others, 2010). Critical thinking involves thinking reflectively and productively and evaluating the evidence. Many of the "Reflect" questions that appear in every section of this book call for critical thinking.

Mindfulness - According to Ellen Langer (1997, 2005), mindfulness is a key to critical thinking. Mind-

fulness means being alert, mentally present, and cognitively flexible while going through life's everyday activities and tasks. Mindful students maintain an active awareness of the circumstances in their lives. Mindful students create new ideas, are open to new information, and are aware of more than one perspective. In contrast, mindless students are entrapped in old ideas, engage in automatic behavior, and operate from a single perspective. Mindless students accept what they read or hear without questioning the accuracy of the information.

Mindless students become trapped in rigid mindsets, not taking into account possible variations in contexts and perspectives. Langer emphasizes that asking good questions is an important ingredient of mindful thinking. She also stresses that it is important to focus on the process of learning rather than the outcome. For example, Trisha didn't do well on her math test earlier this week. All she can think about is how poorly she did. If she were engaging in mindfulness, Trisha would evaluate why she did so poorly and think about what changes she could adopt to do better on the next test.

Creative thinking - An important aspect of thinking is to be able to think creatively (Beghetto & Kaufman, 2010; Sternberg, 2009, 2010a,b). Creativity is the ability to think about something in novel and unusual ways and come up with unique solutions to problems.

J. P. Guilford (1967) distinguished between convergent thinking, which produces one correct answer and is characteristic of the kind of thinking required on conventional intelligence tests, and divergent thinking, which produces many answers to the same question and is more characteristic of creativity. For example, a typical convergent item on a conventional intelligence test is, "How many quarters will you get in return for 60 dimes?" The question has only one right answer. In contrast, divergent questions have many possible answers. For example, consider these questions: "What image comes to mind when you sit alone in a dark room?" and "What are some unique uses for a paper clip?". Are intelligence and creativity related? Although most creative students are quite intelligent (as measured by high scores on conventional intelligence tests), in other respects the reverse is not necessarily true. Many highly intelligent students are not very creative (Kaufman & Sternberg, 2010; Sternberg, 2009, 2010).

Steps in the Creative Process - The creative process is often described as a five-step sequence:

1. *Preparation.* Students become immersed in a problem issue that interests them and their curiosity is aroused.

2. *Incubation.* Students churn ideas around in their head, a point at which they are likely to make some unusual connections in their thinking.

3. *Insight.* Students experience the "Aha!" moment when all pieces of the puzzle seem to fit together.

4. *Evaluation.* Now students must decide whether the idea is valuable and worth pursuing. They need to think, "Is the idea novel or is it obvious?"

5. *Elaboration.* This final step often covers the longest span of time and involves the hardest work. This step is what famous twentieth-century American

inventor Thomas Edison was thinking about when he said that creativity is 1 percent inspiration and 99 percent perspiration.

Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi (1996) argues that this five-step sequence provides a helpful framework for thinking about how to develop creative ideas. However, he emphasizes that creative people don't always go through the steps in a linear sequence. For example, elaboration is often interrupted by periods of incubation. Fresh insights may appear during incubation, evaluation, and elaboration. And insight might take years or only a few hours. Sometimes the creative idea consists of one deep insight. At other times, it is a series of small insights.

Cognitive skills and learning approach of students have special effect on their personal development.

Learning approach

The learning approach refers to the understanding and meaning of the students' learning experience, which is associated with personal (cognitive, affective, and interpersonal) and environmental factors (educational goals, content, methods, materials, resources) that influence and affect the academic processes and outcomes (Marton F., Saljo R., 1976). Knowing the type of approach students prefer and adopt, allows us to understand how students relate to learning tasks, in order to promote the understanding of individual variability at the study level (Paulo M, 2020). Marton and Saljo identified two contrasting approaches: a surface approach and a deep approach to learning (Marton F., Saljo R., 1976; Duarte A.M. ,2002).

The deep approach is characterized by the student's underlying guiding intention to maximize intellectual understanding and extract meaning from the task, i.e., it presupposes the existence of intrinsic motivation. The student seeks to understand and establish relationships between concepts, generalize learning to new concepts, and different situations. Students who take this approach have an active interest in the themes and use logic to understand the concepts (Paulo M, 2020).

The surface approach is characterized by the existence of extrinsic task-oriented motivation and a superficial strategy. This approach is characterized by mechanical and reproductive learning, using the memorization of content, with low commitment and effort on the part of the student, with minimal time spent, but with anxiety to face demanding learning tasks. Surface motivation is considered instrumental, and the student's goal is to learn the minimum necessary to fulfill what is required, pass the exam, and avoid failures (Paulo M, 2020).

Overall, existing studies suggest a significant and positive relationship between the deep learning approach and academic achievement (Paulo M, 2020). Although there are several studies on the coexistence of the two learning approaches, as well as the prominence of each other, the results are inconsistent or have small effects and, therefore, cannot be generalized for all contexts (Diseth A, 2003). This is mainly due to cultural, social, and contextual/learning environment factors.

Regarding personality and academic performance, based on the Big Five Model, studies show that agreeableness and openness to experience are positively associated with motivation for achievement, more effective involvement in educational experiences, and a deeper approach to learning (Chen C., Zhang L.F. ,2011). Conscientiousness is associated with greater objective orientation (Komarraju M., Karau S.J., Schmeck R.R., Avdic A., 2011) and extroversion with mastery, approximation, and performance objectives (Kember D., Biggs J., Leung D.Y.P.,2004). Neuroticism is associated with the avoidance of academic motivation (suggesting that students avoid aspects of academic life) and with a surface learning approach (Duarte A.M, 2007).

Recently, Moreira et al., based on the Psychobiological Model of Personality, used a person-centered approach to assess the relationship between personality profiles and students' preferred approach to learning. Paulo M. found two profiles, one defined by less novelty seeking, greater reward dependence, and persistence that they labeled as "steady" profile, and the second was defined by greater novelty seeking, less reward dependence, and persistence, which was labeled as "disinhibit" profile (Paulo M, 2020). The results suggest that students with a "steady" temperament showed a preference for the deep approach to learning. Students with high character coherence also had this preference. A temperament profile-by-character profile interaction was crucial for understanding students' preferred approach to learning, and implies that adaptive learning approaches result from an integration of the main learning and memory systems, as measured by the Junior Temperament and Character Inventory (JTCI) (Paulo M, 2020).

Conclusions

The results improve the understanding of the differential thinking process, type of learning approach, and academic performance. Understanding that personality is the strongest predictor of thinking process, critical and creative thinking abilities, after controlling the type of learning approach and the thinking style, informs school administration that it is essential to encourage personality development in adolescents to improve thinking skills.

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References

1. Bensley, D. A., Crowe, D. S., Bernhardt, P., Buckner, C., & Allman, A. L. (2010). Teaching and assessing critical thinking skills for argument analysis in psychology. *Teaching of Psychology, 37*(2), 91-96.
2. Beghetto, R. A., & Kaufman, J. C. (Eds.). (2010). *Nurturing creativity in the classroom*. Cambridge University Press.
3. Diseth, Å., & Martinsen, Ø. (2003). Approaches to learning, cognitive style, and motives as predictors of academic achievement. *Educational psychology, 23*(2), 195-207.

4. Chen, C., & Zhang, L. F. (2011). Temperament, personality and achievement goals among Chinese adolescent students. *Educational Psychology, 31*(3), 339-359.
5. Duarte, A. M. (2007). Conceptions of learning and approaches to learning in Portuguese students. *Higher education, 54*, 781-794.
6. Kember, D., Biggs, J., & Leung, D. Y. (2004). Examining the multidimensionality of approaches to learning through the development of a revised version of the Learning Process Questionnaire. *British Journal of Educational Psychology, 74*(2), 261-279.
7. Komarraju, M., Karau, S. J., Schmeck, R. R., & Avdic, A. (2011). The Big Five personality traits, learning styles, and academic achievement. *Personality and individual differences, 51*(4), 472-477.
8. Goswami, N. (2012). Thinking problems. *The Journal of Speculative Philosophy, 26*(2), 189-199.
9. Kinshuk, Lin, T., & McNab, P. (2006). Cognitive trait modelling: the case of inductive reasoning ability. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International, 43*(2), 151-161.
10. Kuhn, D., Katz, J. B., & Dean, Jr, D. (2004). : Developing reason. *Thinking & Reasoning, 10*(2), 197-219.
11. Kuhn, D. (2009). Adolescent thinking.
12. Lee, N. L., Goodwin, G. P., & Johnson-Laird, P. N. (2008). The psychological puzzle of Sudoku. *Thinking & Reasoning, 14*(4), 342-364.
13. Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (1976). On qualitative differences in learning: I—Outcome and process. *British journal of educational psychology, 46*(1), 4-11.
14. Moreira, P., Pedras, S., & Pombo, P. (2020). Students' personality contributes more to academic performance than well-being and learning approach—implications for sustainable development and education. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education, 10*(4), 1132-1149.
15. Ricco, R. B., Koshino, H., Sierra, A. N., Bonssel, J., Monteza, J. V., & Owens, D. N. (2021). Individual differences in analytical thinking and complexity of inference in conditional reasoning. *Thinking & Reasoning, 27*(3), 319-349.
16. Sternberg, R. J., & Kaufman, J. C. (2010). Constraints on creativity. *The Cambridge handbook of creativity, 467-482*.